

The University VP Diptych

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

Adrian Lenardic

Panel 01: I Have Ten Vice Presidents

From the movie Office Space

A lot's been written about how Administrative Bloat is feeding into increased tuition. Administrative growth is tied to universities moving toward business models. Holding to a business view, a question is "Is the increase in administrators leading to an increased Return on Investment (ROI)?" Admins draw salaries which increases the *I* in *ROI*. So, they must also be increasing the *R* or what's the point. Right? **Essay 01** provides in-the-trenches observations related to that question.

Panel 02: Innovation at University.Inc

Street Graffiti Art by Banksy

"It's one of the most absurd ironies of our neoliberal age. Having looted the public realm over the last half century in the name of the free-market, we are suddenly discovering that the last refuge of public virtue is—yes, you guessed it—the private company." It may not be ironic, but it is creepy to have all problems humanity may face packaged as opportunities for entrepreneurship (creepier still to have Universities subscribe to this view). **Essay 02** is about how these issues play into the rebranding of innovation at universities.

I Have Ten Vice Presidents

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

Adrian Lenardic, Rice Univ.

From the movie Office Space

I work at a university that has ten vice presidents.

Better to say that I work at a university that has ten vice presidents, at present. The number has grown and may continue to do so.

The number does not include deans, vice deans, deanettes, provosts or any other administrators that do not have Vice President in their title. It also does not include assistant vice presidents. I don't know how many of those we have – it's not listed on my university's administrative leadership web page.

The increase in administrative staff, VP's being one example, is not unique to my university. Type "administrative bloat universities" into a search engine and you will find ample articles documenting the rise of administrators at universities and within higher education.

Much has been written on how increased university administration is feeding into rising tuitions; How it is connected to the corporatization of universities, with detrimental effects as public goods and public knowledge become privatized and commercialized. How does me, writing yet more, contribute anything of value? Anything of use?

The reality is me saying more may do absolutely nothing. So why write this essay?
Two things.

Firstly, there is an effect of increased administration and corporatization that has not received as much light as it may deserve. It is one that in-the-trenches workers at universities (e.g., me) know about but it doesn't get said a lot (for reasons that I hope will become clear).

Secondly, I was reminded of an exchange with a colleague about a similar issue:

Me: I can't help but feel we may just be talking to each other to make ourselves feel a little better while the machine plows on (it may even be gaining steam).

Colleague: I agree with your feeling, but it makes any tool that keeps one sane even more valuable.

If enough of us perform useless acts of sanity, to shine or re-shine a light on the downsides of university corporatization, then maybe we can hit critical mass of useless acts that fuse into something of use.

So, what grand insights can I shine a light on that university administrators seem to be missing despite sending out survey after survey to the faculty and working staff asking for feedback on various new initiatives that lead to administrative growth; despite setting up 'listening sessions' with various departments. The first insight is not grand at all. It's simple and it's known well by people who have worked at actual companies or corporations (not universities moving toward corporatization). I am pretty sure it's something administrators at successful companies also know well: A clear sign that a company is in trouble is when those who make the company go, the rank and file, start saying "It's just a job".

"It's just a job" is something that can be heard in the trenches. It's not something any worker will be likely to tell an administrator or put on a survey answer (no matter how anonymous the survey is touted as being). If it becomes felt by enough of the rank-and-file workers who make a company go, then it can reverse the trajectory of a once successful company. My second insight is equally simple: If you turn a university of higher education into a business, into a company, into a corporation then you best be prepared for corporate problems that can take the company down. I don't get a sense that university administrators appreciate that. The rise in the number of VP's and administration in general suggests the opposite as it feeds into problems that stagnate companies, e.g., the feeling that "It's just a job".

"It's just a job" is an issue of motivation and passion. Specifically, a lack of motivation beyond a bare minimum. Vice Presidents like to motivate the rank-and-file workers – it helps justify the job. More VP's leads to more motivation to do more. So that should work to keep the passion in the job or to bring it back if it is waning, right? Wrong. Again, I suspect anyone who has had a job at an actual company knows that's wrong. It's so well known that it's been parodied more than once. My personal favorite comes from the movie *Office Space*. The following is an excerpt from the movie script by Mike Judge:

Peter Gibbons: The thing is, Bob, it's not that I'm lazy, it's that I just don't care.

Bob Porter: Don't... don't care?

Peter Gibbons: It's a problem of motivation, all right? Now if I work my ass off and Initech ships a few extra units, I don't see another dime; so where's the motivation? And here's something else, Bob: I have eight different bosses right now.

Bob Slydell: I beg your pardon?

Peter Gibbons: Eight bosses.

Bob Slydell: Eight?

Peter Gibbons: Eight, Bob. So that means that when I make a mistake, I have eight different people coming by to tell me about it. That's my only real motivation is not to be hassled; that, and the fear of losing my job. But you know, Bob, that will only make someone work just hard enough not to get fired."

An added thing to note, for those who have not seen the movie, is that the Peter Gibbons character would not have told the Bobs (who are administrators) what he told them under normal circumstances. It turns out he was hypnotized to be fully care free at work which led him to be totally honest. His critique of the companies move toward more administrators is seen as a breath of fresh air and gets him promoted into the administrative ranks (oh the irony). Eventually he leaves and finds himself in a job he has a passion for.

Passion is something, that if you told me 10 years ago, could be taken out of university faculty members I would have said your crazy. The passion to teach and to do research if one is in the sciences, create if one is in the arts, engage in scholarship if one is in the humanities is, in my experience, what drove my university colleagues far more than pay scales, portfolios, company cash flow, marketable ideas, branding, public relations, pats on the back from VP's, opportunity to rise up the corporate ladder or any of the other things associated with what one might call 'a corporate job'. There was no way that passion could ever be dimmed. Or so I thought.

Before I continue on the main thread, a qualifier is in order.

I realize that this essay could be dismissed an anecdotal. However, things said in 'company' halls but never documented or passed to the higher ups, are not the type of things that can be examined via academic studies, surveys that lead to graphs, and papers with literature citations. They need to be evaluated via the direct experience of individuals. As well as maintaining my sanity, maybe this essay gets readers to ask themselves if they have had similar experiences.

Back to the main.

When I sensed in myself a corporate *deja vu* (I have worked at an actual corporation), at a place I never considered a corporation (i.e., my university), I started to wonder. Wonder turned to conversation. In conversations with colleagues some variant of the following came up more than a few times: "I feel like it's turned into just a job".

Don't get me or my faculty colleagues wrong here: We know that a job is a big deal and do not mean anything demeaning about the value of work when we say "just a job". The meaning is that the passion has been drained out of it. It doesn't matter what job one has (auto body, insurance company, crowd control – I have worked all three), if the passion for it is drained, then good things will not follow (for the worker or the work).

What's an effective way to drain the passion out of the rank and file? Peter Gibbons can tell you (as can many of my university colleagues): Crank up the number of administrators. Have them send the workers more motivation to do more, from increasing angles and written in ever increasing corporate speak, to help the company reach its full potential (whatever that may be – shroud it in more corporate or branding speak to really drain passion). Increase the administrative chain so it's clear to workers that they no longer have the power to influence agendas in any real way (just too long a chain that takes too much time and effort for information to move through). Increase the number of forms that need to be filled out (especially if you want to do anything 'new'). Make workers compete against each other for company resources (with more forms to fill out, or proposals to write, for the competitions). Put in new software systems, with associated mandatory training, to 'help' the workers navigate the increasing administrative webs that 'support' the corporation.

My corporate speak is rusty but I can end with a corporate speak question to ponder. Corporations like to talk about return on investment (*ROI*). Is the rise of university administrators leading to an increased *ROI*? Administrators draw salaries which increases the *I* in the *ROI*. So, they must also be increasing the *R* in *ROI* or what would be the point (what corporation would be silly enough to create more administrative positions that lead to no positive changes or, at best, to no change at all).

What is the return a university provides to students and parents and to society in general? Not an easy question. Not one I have a simple answer to. I have an opinion as to a key factor (arguably the critical factor). To me, the return universities provide is driven by the passions of the rank-and-file workers at the university – the passions that at one time were, in my experience, the antithesis of “It’s just a job” but that are being drained by rising administration.

In the corporatization of universities, which comes with increased metrics used to evaluate performance, passion is easily mis-valued or mis-read as it does not lend itself to quantitative metrics. Its quality needs to be seen and felt from in the trenches (the very place many administrators left long ago for greener pastures). My observations from in the trenches may be outliers but they make me think that the rise of administrative universities will progressively lower the *ROI* of universities. Can it be turned around? I hope so but I also worry that it has moved well above my company level and the level of the people who actually support the university ... or should I say the corporation.

**“I’m naming you VP of Revolution, Action and Edgy Thinking ...
on one condition ...
that you promise not to change anything.”**

Cartoon from modernanalyst.com

https://www.modernanalyst.com/Resources/BusinessAnalystHumor/tabid/218/ID/3827/VP_of_Innovation.aspx

Innovation at University.Inc

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

Adrian Lenardic.

I am a professor at a university in the United States. My university recently experienced a binary fission. In a moment of administrative mitosis, the Vice President of Research divided into a Vice President of Research *and* a Vice President of Innovation [1]. The salary was not split into two, I am reasonably sure.

The fission was noticeable in my email inbox. Vice Presidents like to motivate the workers – it justifies the job. Now the motivation was to do more research and to be more innovative. I was informed that research, on its own, is not innovative – hence the need for two VP's [2].

Beyond that, it was not clear to me what *innovation* meant to the powers that be who felt we needed a new vice president of it. If the university was innovative, then we would not really need a VP of innovation, would we? Had we become un-innovative? Had we ever been innovative? Maybe we weren't innovative enough? Maybe we needed a VP to help us reach our innovative potential. If we did reach it, would a VP of Innovation become obsolete? Was I being less than innovative?

All sorts of rabbit holes popped into my mind. I could have gone deep down them save for one of those motivational emails.

To my innovation VP's credit, an email saved me the exercise of pondering what being more innovative means and wondering how that would be assessed. A few excerpts made it clear what innovation meant to my universities newly formed office of innovation [3]:

"How do we translate your research into the market?"

"...making sure that your hard work has a clear trajectory and support to get to market."

"... from Research to Innovation through marketing of your technology and rapid licensing to startups or established companies."

"... provides a clear glide path for transitioning inventions from your lab into the market."

Ah yes, The Market. The entity that decides what is of value and what is not. Why wouldn't it also be the arbitrator of what is innovative. The email also informed me that we would hire an assistant vice president of commercialization who would work with our assistant vice president of technology transfer [4].

I was dis-heartened that innovation was a buzzword for commercialization. Call me an idealist. Call me naïve. Corporatization of universities is nothing new [5]. Increasing privatization of science, including science done at universities, is also not a new trend [6].

If innovation has become commercialization and money flow, then so it is. Those silly idealists of us, who don't agree with corporate models of universities or who are incapable of 'getting with the program', still have research and discovery to fall back on, independent of whether it leads to increased cash flow. Right?

Wrong.

How did I know I was wrong?

Another email from another VP, this time the VP of research, told me.

Here is a snippet (with actual numbers removed):

In the Office of Research, we are working on some ideas to help spur a growth in our research portfolio, which invariably means that we need to submit more proposals. Currently our hit rate is about xx% ... we were funded at \$yyyM level. A simple scaling would suggest that we could increase the \$yyyM to a higher value by writing more proposals.

Portfolios and increased cash flow are not the things I was taught about by mentors who trained me in science. They reflect a view of science that is detrimental to science itself [7]. They are not the things (in my experience) that drew my faculty colleagues (across more than a single department) to academics. They could be the things that cause many creative people to opt out of academia or not enter it at all.

If universities operate like corporations, with the downsides but without the equivalent monetary upside for those who work there (not including those who administrate there), then why wouldn't the next generation bypass universities and go into industry? If universities become ever more corporate, then won't this push out creative individuals who don't have interests, tendencies, or foundations in market style competitions for personal gains? Isn't that working against increased diversity in academics and in science?

More question popped into my head [8]. One of them was a practical one. If I accept a move to corporatization of universities (I don't), there is then a business-driven question: Why pay high administrative salaries for research and for innovation if the two have the same end-goal? Couldn't the two have remained one? What justifies two VPs?

I could have wandered down a rabbit hole of ever more questions for every question I answered save for a third email. The key line was "*The Vice President of Innovation will work closely with the Vice President of Research.*" That pairs with the excerpt from the office of innovation about the flow from '*Research to Innovation, via marketing, to licensing with startups or established companies.*'

It was now clear to me what innovation meant to universities that felt the need to appoint VPs, officers, and/or Provosts of innovation. It was presented to me as simple as day - From *Research to Innovation*:

Research (getting public resources, via government funded grants, to develop ideas and/or technologies)

to Innovation (transforming/re-framing the ideas/technologies into innovations to be commercialized for private profits).

Clever [9, 10].

The closest clever idea I know of, for taking publicly funded work and turning it into private profit while denying public access (unless they pay), is academic publishing [11, 12].

A drive for "innovative" ideas (i.e., ones primed for commercialization) is in line with the growth of business schools at universities and a focus on entrepreneurial and leadership training for students [13]. It's in synch with universities adopting business models based on the idea that companies competing with each other is the most productive way to move the economy forward. The re-branding of research and innovation adds a spin by promoting the view that privatization is the best way to get innovations to the public for greater societal

good. A view taught to students and promoted to faculty. If I was innovative, I would trademark a slogan for innovative universities: *Private Profits for the Public Good*.

I had answers for my initial questions about the re-branding of innovation at universities, but I was left confused. I can sum up my confusion with a bit of sarcasm: When I think who can lead us in responsible and ethical innovation for the public good, even if decisions along the way may not align with private profits, my first thought is certainly CEOs of corporation and/or hungry entrepreneurs eager to establish their new startups.

The irony of universities of higher education touting that faculty and students could best serve the public good by linking with established companies and startups seemed so thick, so much a scheme to pre-justify a drive for profit, so lacking in honesty, that I was left looking at the sky and asking myself “Am I the only one seeing this?”.

I was pleasantly surprised to find that someone who has been called an entrepreneur had noticed a similar irony outside of the university walls [14]:

It's one of the most absurd ironies of our neoliberal age. Having looted the public realm over the last half century in the name of the free-market, we are suddenly discovering that the last refuge of public virtue is—yes, you guessed it—the private company. The only thing we “trust,” these days, we are told, are supposedly public-spirited corporations This moral ponzi scheme, then, is repackaging private enterprise as public virtue. It's a fittingly tragicomic final act to the twilight years of our neoliberal age. Business schools, the seminaries of neoliberalism, have been teaching this nonsense for years.

The vice-presidential fission at my university taught me the degree to which the above continues to be taught, now with new and improved leadership training (trademark pending), and how it is being messaged to faculty, post-docs, and all researchers who might have innovative (i.e., marketable) ideas that can solve societal problems for private profits.

A current societal problem is climate change. Many students, eager to address it, are coming into universities with interests in environmental studies. My university, like many, now has an environmental initiative – it has already become connected to research and innovation offices. Future generations do have the potential to solve ecological problems for the public good. And herein an absurd irony. We have a new generation interested in serving the public good by addressing environmental problems that affect all citizens of the planet, whether they can or cannot pay for university education or any intellectual products that come from universities. What the students get taught when they come to university is that the way to do public good is through private enterprise that lets them get the commercial rewards they deserve [15].

The irony above connects to a gamble on the future: The gamble that the invisible hand of the market is the best means for addressing climate change and associated ecological problems. Although ecology can be turned into a means for added market competition, with private investments and gains/losses, the scope of the problems we are facing may go beyond the abilities of “market reason” [16]. The gamble is no longer one of companies losing profits to the competition as market forces sort things out over time. It is a collective gamble. It doesn't break down to competitors pushing to get the most marketable ‘solution’ to the market, while at the same time not sharing potentially profitable ideas or, if you like, innovations. It may not be ironic, but it is, to me at least, creepy to have all problems humanity may face packaged as opportunities for entrepreneurship [17, 18].

There is an old school view that innovation is more about creativity than marketability. Holding to that, I will end with quote from a collection of essays by David Bohm on creativity. The quote, made before climate change and environmental/ecological issues became prominent, shows the absurdity and dangers of privatizing public good, particularly when the public good is environmental [19]:

If, without their knowing it, the people who study ecology and try to apply their knowledge of it are themselves committed to their own personal interests, or to the interests of their own economic, political, social, or national groups, how can they allow the whole to be the first in their thoughts? Inevitably, there will be subliminal pressures and tendencies to think in a fragmentary way that would seem to be appropriate to what is believed to be the overwhelming necessity of putting personal or group interests first. Thus, it will not be possible intelligently to think of and talk about all aspects that are relevant to the totality of the ecological cycles of the planet.

...

What, then, is the value of calls to political, social, or economic action, when we are unable to give proper attention to what we are doing because our minds are in a state of chaos through looking at everything, including ourselves, in a fragmentary way?

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Acknowledgements: Several friends and colleagues provided valuable feedback on this essay: John Traphagan, Andrea Saltelli, Jerome Ravetz, and Bjoern Brembs to name a few. I very much appreciate it. Peter Murray-Rust provided an email comment that was so spot on to me, I will include a portion of it here: *"I've worked in (well-funded) industry - pharma - for 15 years and the last thing they want is academic innovation into the market. They want to work with and hire really good people from academia, they want academia to explore new ideas in public. I've seen a company waste 250M (10+ years ago) by not reading the public literature. I'd say that pharma needs **more** pre-competitive research Having university fight university destroys the system."*

Art by Banksy

Notes and References

- [1] Innovation does not relate to innovations in education. It is about innovations connected to research carried out at a university. In the past, many universities considered a VP of Research to be, in effect, a VP of Research and Innovation. Some universities called that out explicitly in the VP title while for others it was more implicit.

- [2] I had, before the binary fission, thought that research was innovative. Clearly, I was wrong if one administrative staff was now required to oversee research while another administrative staff was required to oversee innovation.
- [3] A new administrator can't achieve significant goals without an *Office of Something* (or so the argument goes). Sometimes it's not an *Office Of* but a newly formed *Institute* or a campus wide *Initiative*.
- [4] Assistant vice presidents are needed to support vice presidents if a new *institute* or *office of something* or *initiative* is to reach bold new worlds (or so the argument goes). There may also be *lecture series* to help galvanize support for new *initiatives*. My university had a series titled "*Betterment of the World*". A main speaker, the head of a new entrepreneurship initiative, was advertised to be discussing "*the challenges in commercializing university research discoveries and how to overcome these variables to help more basic research move from the lab to market for the betterment of all.*"
- [5] Maisuria, A., and Helmes, S. (2019) *Life for the Academic in the Neoliberal University*, Abingdon, Oxon: Taylor & Francis; Mittelman, J.H. (2018) *Implausible Dream: The World-Class University and Repurposing Higher Education*, Princeton: Princeton University Press; Slaughter, S., and Leslie, L.L. (1997) *Academic Capitalism: Politics, Policies, and the Entrepreneurial University*, Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press; Smyth, J. (2017) *The Toxic University: Zombie Leadership, Academic Rock Stars, and Neoliberal Ideology*, London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- [6] Krinsky, S. (2004) *Science in the Private Interest*, Rowman & Littlefield Publishers; Mirowski, P. (2011) *Science-Mart*, Cambridge: Harvard University Press; Cohen, D. and Mikaelian, A. (2021) *The Privatization of Everything*, London: Chelsea Green Publishing.
- [7] In 1972, Jerome Ravetz foresaw the dangers that come from corporate models applied to science. They are part of his "four horsemen of the scientific apocalypse in the form of shoddy science, entrepreneurial science, reckless science, and dirty science" (Ravetz, Jerome R., 1979, *Scientific Knowledge and Its Social Problems*, Oxford: Oxford Univ. Press). His definition of entrepreneurial science applies to the way university leadership now views the role of funding: "that which occurs when a series of scientifically adequate research projects enables a series of financially successful grants, rather than the successful projects depending on adequate grants."
- [8] What if I can do decent research for cheap, even for no cost to government agencies that academic scientists write proposals to? Would I be helping to increase my universities research portfolio? I sat on review panels for the National Science Foundation and NASA. They are already stressed. So, what happens when the number of submitted proposals doubles. How will peer review remain fair if an already stressed workload is increased? Do my colleagues have time to write more quality proposals given they already write a lot, are asked to review a lot, and have that pesky teaching-education thing getting in the way? Maybe the answers will come from what I foresee as the Vice President of Artificial Intelligence. The VP of AI will motivate faculty to use AI (e.g., ChatGPT) to write research proposals. Proposals can also be reviewed by AI. That would make more market sense than recruiting more peer reviewers and/or panel members who should be writing more proposals versus reviewing them (if you see a worrisome feedback here, that can take humans out of the loop, then you're not 'with the program').

The VP of AI would, I am sure, discover many more things at a university that could be replaced by AI ... except, of course, administrative positions.

- [9] The clever idea also ‘justifies’ two vice presidents: One deals with negotiating research grants, which come from publicly funded programs, while the other deals with the private sector. Plus, the vice president of research can still motivate faculty members who have research ideas that can generate grant funding but that are not innovative in the sense that they can flow to the purvey of the vice president of innovation.
- [10] I could have referred to the idea as innovative but clever seemed more fitting. While writing, an image popped into my head from one of the *Jurassic Park* movies. In the scene a dinosaur hunter is about to fire on a velociraptor when he realizes he has walked into a trap. He can’t help but admire the cunningness of the velociraptors when he realizes what has happened and what is about to happen. He looks into the eyes of the velociraptor that made him aware of the trap and says: “Clever.”
- [11] Monbiot, G. (2011) Academic publishers make Murdoch look like a socialist, *The Guardian*, <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2011/aug/29/academic-publishers-murdoch-socialist> ; Haack, S. (2019) The Academic-Publication Racket: Whatever Happened to Authors’ Rights? *Borderless Philosophy*, 2, 1-21; Neff, M.W. (2020) How Academic Science Gave Its Soul to the Publishing Industry, *Issue in Science and Technology*, 36 (2), 35-43; Yup, K. (2023) How Scientific Publishers’ Extreme Fees Put Profit Over Progress, <https://www.thenation.com/article/society/neuroimage-elsevier-editorial-board-journal-profit/>
- [12] The publishing connection makes it clear I have no chance of being innovative as I am opposed to privatization of academic knowledge: Brembs, B., Lenardic, A., Murray-Rust, P., Chan, L. and Erwin Irawan, D. (2023) Mastodon over Mammon - Towards publicly owned scholarly knowledge, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7974099>. I’m so not with it that I even interact with people researching ways to make scientific findings accessible to the public for free (how un-innovative). I have nothing against private companies or startups. I have interacted with companies, one was a startup, for a science outreach project (<https://roadsidescience.wordpress.com/2013/12/07/skate-park-physics/>). I have given presentations at startup workshops (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yZqE-HoNR1Y>) and consult on development of startup training courses. What I have issues with is morphing public knowledge and public goods into private goods to be sold back to the public, especially when the public has already supported the work. I realize that, starting with the Bayh-Dole act of 1980, all of this is legal but legal and ethical are not equivalent.
- [13] Parker, M. (2018) Why We Should Bulldoze the Business School, *The Guardian*, <https://www.theguardian.com/news/2018/apr/27/bulldoze-the-business-school> ; Smyth, J. (2020) The Making of Bullshit Leadership and Toxic Management in the Neoliberal University, *Social Epistemology Review and Reply Collective*, 9 (5), 9-18 <https://wp.me/p1Bfg0-50m>
- [14] Keen, A. (2022) Neoliberal Pieties and Business School Empathy Aren’t Getting Us Out of This Mess, *Literature Hub*, <https://lithub.com/neoliberal-pieties-and-business-school-empathy-arent-getting-us-out-of-this-mess/>

- [15] Universities have become good at teaching students, now viewed as customers, that their education is about getting the training they deserve to get what they deserve in the free market (e.g., Madary, E. (2023) Where Rich Students Are Told: 'You Deserve This', *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, <https://www.chronicle.com/article/where-rich-students-are-told-you-deserve-this>). *Deserve* is a short step from *entitled to* and a philosopher (an un-innovative profession) has defined an asshole as someone who "allows himself to enjoy special advantages in social relations out of an entrenched sense of entitlement that immunizes him against the complaints of other people." (James, A. (2012), *Assholes: A Theory*, New York: Doubleday). In the same book there is the thought (I am paraphrasing) that if one wants more assholes in the world, then replace more humanities departments with business schools.
- [16] Žižek, S., (2008), *Censorship Today: Violence, or Ecology as the New Opium, for the Masses*, <https://www.lacan.com/zizecology1.htm> ; Monbiot, G. (2021) *Capitalism is Killing the Planet*, *The Guardian*, <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2021/oct/30/capitalism-is-killing-the-planet-its-time-to-stop-buying-into-our-own-destruction>
- [17] A definition of Entrepreneur from the Urban Dictionary: What drug dealers put in their Instagram bio <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=Entrepreneur> . I am not implying a blanket view of entrepreneurship. Just the opposite. There is good, there is bad and there is the potential of hiding the reality of a particular situation behind a generic label. What is worrisome is how Entrepreneurship, of a type focused on marketability and profit, is being advertised as the greatest value to students and to academia. In the process, ethics takes a back seat (beyond absurd online 'training' videos on ethics). There is an analogy that comes to my mind as a fan of international football. Many students of the game find it worrisome that players are being coached to "gain an advantage" which, in every day language, translates to anything between stretching the rules and cheating in a way that doesn't get you caught.
- [18] There is an added irony. Many Earth and Environmental Scientists express how they want to do public good in the face of climate change and environmental challenges and yet resistance to privatization of knowledge related to environmental issues is rare from that same group of scientists. It's as if the majority of scientists wanting to do public good are happy to fall in line with universities seeking to pair with private corporations and startups with the thought that there will be no conflict of interests. It is ironic that generally skeptical, in a good way, people are willing to put faith in administrators, company CEO's and hungry entrepreneurs seeking to launch startups with a "what could go wrong?" attitude.
- [19] Bohm, D. (1996), *On Creativity*, Routledge, New York:NY

After the Fact

The following notes were added after the main two essays in the Academic VP Diptych were finished and had been posted on Future U. The links to the Future U versions:

<https://futureu.education/uncategorized/commentary-i-have-ten-vice-presidents/>

and

<https://futureu.education/higher-ed/commentary-by-adrian-lenardic-innovation-at-university-inc/>

This first essay, “I Have Ten Vice-Presidents”, was published in June 2023.

Its title was accurate at that time.

As of July 2023, the title should be changed to “I Have Twelve Vice-Presidents”.

As of March 2024, the title should be changed to “I Have Thirteen Vice-Presidents”.

The thirteenth vice president is The VP of Capital Planning and is also the President of my Universities Real Estate Company.

If you are wondering why a university of higher education, scholarship, and research would need a president of real estate, then this is worth a read: Baldwin, D.L. (2021), *In the Shadow of the Ivory Tower: How Universities Are Plundering Our Cities*, New York: Bold Type Books.

The version of the second essay included in this diptych is not the version that appeared in print at Future U. The version included here is the original. The posted version was toned down a touch and generalized. The original is more about what I directly experienced. That experience did lead to me to look at other universities and see that similar things are happening across the university system. Had the changes I saw happening been unique to my university I would not have been motivated to write the essay. The two versions are not that different in content but maybe the more personalized version can be of some added worth to the masses of three or four people who might glance at it.